

The Influence of Organizational Culture and Work Motivation on Employee Performance in the Millennial and Gen Z Era

(Case Study of Teachers in Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta)

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Abstract:- This study aims to find out and analyze the influence of organizational culture, and work motivation on employee performance in the millennial dan gen z era at Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta. This research is a quantitative study. The population in this study was 70 teachers of Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta. The sampling method in this study used purposive sampling, with the sample technique using non-probability sampling. Then the sample in this study was determined, namely the permanent teachers of the millennial generation and z totaled 45 people. The data analysis method of this study uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the help of SmartPLS software version 3.2.9. The results of this study show that organizational culture and work motivation affect the performance of millennial and gen z teachers at Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta.

Keywords:- Organizational Culture, Work Motivation, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

During the second term of President Joko Widodo and Vice President Mar'uf Amin (2019-2024), they began to focus on material strength in human resources (HR). This is because, Indonesia faces fierce competition, especially in providing vocational high school (SMK), senior high school (SMA) or university graduates certainly need quality human resources. This is in accordance with the industry competition in Indonesia that faces the ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) which has been felt and also every country or workforce in ASEAN will compete together to become superior in creating the best human resources. In facing the AEC, of course, the Indonesian government and also educators in Indonesia play a big role in dealing with this. This can be seen from various points of view that school participation in Indonesia will continue to increase every year and be able to create fierce competition [1].

The success of an educational institution can be determined by the quality of human resources and also other supporting means. This is because these two aspects have an important role in advancing the value of the quality of human

resources. Without the active role of employees, goals cannot be achieved, despite the highly developed equipment of the organization. One of the key factors in achieving national education goals is the educators or teachers who are in schools. This is because the teacher will provide direction and always teach students to be able to be a superior resource and be able to provide good direction for their future. Teachers have a big role in the success of human resources because teachers make every student to be the best in various aspects. This makes the role of the teacher very large and noble. Every teacher certainly wants superior and creative people so that they can bring great changes to Indonesia.

Most of the teachers in the school are Millennials. In terms of age group, most teachers are aged 30-39 years. There are 851,316 teachers in this age group. This figure is equivalent to 29.29 percent of 2,906,239 Indonesian teachers [1]. However, the next largest division consists of teachers who are approaching retirement age. A total of 793,780 teachers aged 50-59 years or 27.31 Indonesian teachers. Then as many as 691,531 teachers aged 0-9 years or 23.79%. The Ministry of Education and Culture reported that there were 51,233 teachers between the ages of 20 and 29. There are also 3,988 teachers under the age of 1 in Indonesia [2].

Differences between generations have different ways of thinking and character, therefore they form their own personalities and even paradigms [3]. In the past hundred years, five generations have been formed, that is. Baby Boomers were born before 1960, Generation X was born between 1961-1980, Generation Y (Millennials) were born 1981-1994, Generation Z was born 1995 -2010. Generation Alpha born between 2010 and today [4]. There are generational differences, companies must provide a work culture according to existing conditions, so that companies remain competitive to get a standard workforce as needed [5].

Those with a strong culture, that is those who have an understanding of the core values of the organization, can win the competition [6]. The most significant characteristic difference between generations X, Y and Z is mastery For generation Z, information and technology are things that have become part of their lives, because they were born where access to the internet has become this year, on average in the

world of education, the generation that is most currently studying and pursuing a job career is the millennial generation. Where millennials usually like something out of the box. Millennials tend to create an environment of college, work and daily conversation This suggests that millennials prefer all forms of Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta in Central Jakarta and East Jakarta organized by the Tribina Education Foundation.

Jayawisata 1 Vocational High School Central Jakarta and Jayawisata 2 Vocational High School East Jakarta have teachers from the millennial generation and even generation Z with dedication must be able to support the application of technology or support services and infrastructure that can help the organizational system of SMK Jayawisata Jakarta to operate at Jayawisata Vocational High School so that the vision and mission can be realized. Teachers have a big role in advancing education and the quality of human resources. This is regulated in Presidential Regulation number 74 of 2008 to improve human resources, especially in students. Presenting the work as a whole. Jayawisata Vocational High School

Jakarta is a vocational high school that was established in 1977 domiciled in Central Jakarta under the name Jayawisata 1 Vocational High School Jakarta and East Jakarta under the name Jayawisata 2 Vocational High School Jakarta with special programs namely the tourism, hospitality, catering and multimedia service industries.

In carrying out the activities of the Learning Program of Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta must be carried out professionally and empowered by individuals who are reliable, professional and have high integrity. This is because teachers have a big role to play for the future of each of their students. Teachers become one of the educators who are involved in the future of each student and provide good direction. Teachers at Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta consist of Permanent Teachers of Millennial Generation and Generation Z with the age of 24 to 39 years and Permanent Teachers of Generation X and Baby Boomers with the age of over 40 years. In table 2 the following are the number of teachers of Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta.

Table 1: Number of Teachers at Jayawisata VHS Jakarta

School Name	Number of Permanent Teachers Ages 24 -39	Number of Permanent Teacher Age 40 and above
Jayawisata 1 VHS Central Jakarta	20	10
Jayawisata 2 VHS Jakarta	25	15
Total Teachers	45	25

The factors that affect teacher performance at Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta are the variables of Compensation, Workload, Organizational Culture, Training, Leadership and Work Motivation. And from the Results of Teacher Polls Generation Y (Millennial) and Gen Z at Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta are Work Motivation (95%), Organizational Culture (85%), Compensation (80%), Transformational Leadership (75%), Workload (80%), and Training (75%). The two most powerful variables that are thought to affect the performance of generation Y (Millennial) and gen Z teachers are Work Motivation (95%), Organizational Culture (85%). Of the variables that most affect Teacher Performance at Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta, Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta focuses on the variables of Organizational Culture and Work Motivation.

II. LITERATURE

A. Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is a value that all members of the organization believe in and that are learned, applied and developed on an ongoing basis, function as an adhesive system, and can be used as a reference for behavior in the organization to achieve company goals that have been set so as to emphasize organizational values and the beliefs of each employee to be internalized in every task and function so as to create effectiveness [7].

B. Work Motivation

Work motivation is closely related to a person's performance or performance. Basically, a person's work motivation is different. There is high work motivation and there is low work motivation, if the work motivation is high, it will affect high performance and vice versa if the motivation is low it will cause the performance that a person has is low. If the employee has high work motivation, he will work hard, diligently, happily, and with high dedication so that the results are in accordance with the goals to be achieved [8].

C. Employee Performance

Performance is the result of work that a person achieves based on job requirements. To determine the performance of an employee is good or not good, depending on the results of his comparison with the standards of his work. Performance standards are the level that a particular job is expected to complete and are a comparison of the goals or targets to be achieved [9].

Employee performance as one of the important things to be able to manage and allocate the amount of power they have to be able to make a good performance standard for them. The performance of employees will affect the work of the employees themselves. Thus, employee performance will have an influence on several other indicators. Employee performance will always be compared to employee engagement and other performance so that it will affect existing results [10].

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Based on previous research, the framework developed in the research is as follows.

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework

Based on the picture above, there are seven hypotheses in this study, namely:

H1 : There is an influence of organizational culture on employee performance in Generation Y (Millennial) and Z Teachers at Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta.

H2 : There is an influence of work motivation on employee performance in Millennial Gennerasi Teachers Y (Millennial) and Z at Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta.

IV. RESEARCH AND METHODS

This research is a quantitative study with an explanatory or causal design. This study examines the influence of organizational culture and work motivation on employee performance. The sampling technique used in this study is non-probability sampling, which is a sampling technique that does not provide equal opportunities or opportunities for each element or member of the population to be selected as a sample. Therefore, based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that the population mentioned in this study is 70 teachers who teach at SMK Jayawisata Jakarta, while the sample is permanent teachers, as many as 45 millennial and z generation teachers who meet the criteria to be used as sample teachers. To be able to measure the relationship between organization culture, work motivation to employee performance, researchers conduct multivariate using SEM-PLS software. SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) using SmartPLS software version 3.2.9 with a process through computerized media.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This study used a sample of 45 respondents, namely permanent teachers of generation Y (Millennial) and Z at Jayawisata Vocational High School with the data collection was the distribution of questionnaires to 45 respondents of permanent teachers of generation Y (Millennial) and Gen Z in Jayawisata Vocational High School, after which the respondents answered the statements given. All respondents' statements are expected to provide a true picture of the conditions at the study site. In the previous analysis of the results of this study, an analysis was carried out on the picture of respondents grouped according to gender, group, last

education and length of service. The estimation of this external model determines how each indicator relates to its latent variables.

The analysis process is carried out by running the calculation of the PLS algorithm program with SmartPLS version 3.2.9. After that look at the results of calculations with excel reports. With the results of the analysis, it is checked whether the measurement results used can be used as a measuring instrument (correct and reliable). The results of the analysis of this reflective external model can be seen in several indicators, namely:

A. Convergent Validity

An indicator is considered to have a high level of validity if it has a loading factor value greater than 0.70 [11]. However, indicators that have a loading factor of 0.50 to 0.60 ($\alpha > 0.70$) are still acceptable. The results of the validity test showed that all loading factors of each indicator using all variables, namely: financial compensation, organizational culture, work motivation, employee performance and employee commitment were above 0.7. This proves that all indicators used are valid or have met convergent validity. Therefore, the decision of the researcher is to include all these statements. Statements on organizational culture statement variables as many as 7 statements work motivation as many as 12 statements and employee performance as many as 10 statements that will be used.

B. Discriminat Validity

Test the validity of the second stage, ie. discriminant validity test. This test is based on cross-loading measure values with constructs and AVE (Average Variance Extracted) values. The cross-loading factor determines whether a latent variable has sufficient distinguishing power by comparing the correlation between the indicator and other latent variables [11]. If the correlation value of a construct with a measured item is greater than the value of correlation with other constructs, this indicates that the latent construct predicts the magnitude of a variable based on its cross-loading value better than the size of the cross-loading value. Other variables and constructs are said to have greater discriminant validity.

Based on indicators from all variables, namely, organizational culture, work motivation, and employee performance are higher than correlation. values with other structures. Thus, it can be concluded that all latent constructs show good discriminant validity, since they can predict the cross-loading value of organizational culture, work motivation and employee performance variables better than the indicators. other variables. Furthermore, discriminant validity testing is carried out by looking at the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value. AVE values are good if they have a value greater than 0.50 [11].

Variable	AVE Value
Organizational Culture	0,662
Work motivation	0,606
Employee Performance	0,776

Table 2: AVE (Average Variance Extraction) Results from the Research Model

The results of the Discriminant Validity test conducted by looking at the AVE value can be explained that the AVE value of the research model shown in above is for all variables of organizational culture, work motivation and employee performance t the value of the variable is greater than 0.5, then the AVE value of the Discriminant Validity test meets the requirements for subsequent testing. Thus, the Discriminant Validity test and the Convergen Validity test.

C. Reliability Testing (Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha)

Reliability tests are designed to determine how reliable a measuring device is or reliable. A survey is said to be reliable or trustworthy if the answers to the questions are consistent or stable over time [12]. The reliability of the indicators in this study was determined based on the composite reliability and value of Cronbach's alpha of each indicator block using the PLS method. The rule of thumb for alpha or combined reliability must be greater than 0.7, although a value of 0.6 is still acceptable.

➤ **Composite Reliability**

Another test for evaluating external models is to look at the reliability of latent variable constructs measured by two measures, namely the composite reliability of the indicator block that measures the construct and Cronbach's alpha. In the early stages, a construct is declared reliable if its composite reliability value is above 0.70 [11]. Here are the external model results for combined reliability.

Variable	Composite Reliability
Organizational Culture	0,932
Work motivation	0,948
Employee Performance	0,972

Table 3: Composite Reliability Results of Research Models

Table 3 shows the combined reliability of the research model, which shows that the combined reliability of each variable is above 0.7, with the lowest score of 0.932 for organizational culture change (X2) and the highest value of 0.972 for employee performance change (Y). From these results, it can be concluded that the research model meets the value of composite reliability.

➤ **Cronbach's Alpha**

The next step in reliability testing is Cronbach's Alpha testing. A construct is declared reliable if its cronbach's alpha value is above 0.60 [11]. Here are Cronbach's alpha results for the outer model:

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
Organizational Culture	0,914
Work Motivation	0,940
Employee Performance	0,968

Table 4: Cronbach's Alpha Results from a Research Model

Table 4 shows the Cronbach's Alpha values of the research model showing that each variable has a Cronbach's Alpha value above 0.6, the lowest value of 0.91 for the Organizational Culture variable (X2), and the highest value of 0.968 for the Employee Performance (Y) variable. From these

results, it can be concluded that the research model meets the value of Cronbach's Alpha. From the above model, it can be concluded that the model meets the criteria of Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha, so that the research model meets the reliability criteria and is a reliable and trustworthy measurement instrument.

D. Coefficient of Determination Test / R Square (R²)

The purpose of the coefficient of determination is to measure how well the model can explain the variance of the endogenous variable. The value of the coefficient of determination is between 0 and 1. The value of the coefficient of determination (R²) is close to 1. The value of R-squared (R²) describes how much the exogenous variable assumed in the equation is able to explain the endogenous variable. The results of the determination test are presented in the table below.

Variable	R Square
Employee Performance	0,998

Table 5: Coefficient of Determination Test Results

As shown in Table 5, the R-squared value of the Employee Performance variable is 0.998 which means that 99.8% of the Employee Performance variable can be influenced by the Organizational Culture and Work Motivation variables, while the remaining 0.2% is influenced by variables other than those studied.

E. Measuring Effect Size f²

F square or effect size is another name for the effect of changing R square, the value of f square can be obtained from the formulation (original R² – R²) that has been omitted) / (1- R² original). The equation of the f square value describes how much of the proportion of unexplained variance is taken into account by the change of R². A value of 0.02 represents "weak", 0.15 represents "medium", and 0.35 represents "strong" [13]. Table 6 is the results of the f² test as follows.

Variable	Employee Performance
Organizational Culture	0,600
Work Motivation	0,592

Table 6: f Square Results

f-square test result in table 6, explains that the organizational culture variable has a moderate effect size in affecting employee performance of 0.600. The work motivation variable has a moderate effect size in affecting employee performance of 0.592. From these results, it can be interpreted that strong employee performance not only increases employee efficiency and productivity, but also increases employee loyalty and commitment in accordance with the organization culture, where work culture encourages employee adaptation, the organizational environment is in accordance with organizational culture values exist in the organization and maintain these values as guidelines for employees to apply in their duties and work, and work motivation is one of the drivers of employee performance that leads to high productivity.

F. Hypothesis Test

The path coefficient values, t-statistic and p-value were used in this study to test hypotheses. Hypothesis testing was carried out on 45 respondents using SmartPLS (Partial Least Square) software as shown in the bootstrap results. The rule used in this study is t-statistic > 1.96 or p-value is 0.05 (5%) then it can be concluded that there is a significant influence between exogenous and endogenous variables.

Through the results of data processing, the level of significance of the relationship is also obtained to see whether the hypothesis is significant or insignificant. The relationship between variables can be assessed through the path coefficient column, while for the degree of significance it can be assessed through the T-statistical or P-value column, as follows:

Variable Relationships	Original Sample	T Statistics	P-Values	Conclusion
Organizational Culture > Employee Performance	0,225	3,979	0,000	H1 Accepted
Work Motivation > Employee Performance	0,183	5,192	0,000	H2 Accepted

Table 7: Path Coefficient, t-Statistics, and P-Values Results

In this process the determination of the basis for decision making on the value of t counts. Where t count is obtained from the value of path coefficient analysis, while t table is obtained by looking at the table of percentage points of distribution of t based on significant degree and degree of freedom.

VI. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, it is known that the organizational culture variable for employee performance has a path coefficient value of +0.225 with a calculated t value of 3.979 > 1.98 and a p-value of 0.000 < 0.05. Thus, organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Jayawisata Vocational High School. With a work culture, it will make it easier for employees to adjust to the organizational environment and help employees to know what actions should be taken in accordance with the values in the organization and uphold these values as a guideline for employees to behave that can be carried out in carrying out their duties and work.

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, it is known that the work motivation variable for employee performance has a path coefficient value of +0.183 with a calculated t value of 5.192 > 1.98 and a p-value of 0.000 < 0.05. Thus, work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Jayawisata Vocational High School. Work motivation can provide considerable support in improving work performance, work productivity, and organizational commitment. Motivation will also affect a person's attitude and behavior in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. Strong weak work motivation will determine the high and low level of performance of employees or employees. With motivation, an employee will feel that he has a special drive to complete a job towards achieving organizational effectiveness. The advice given to the management in this case the Foundation as the organizer of education and the principal as the highest leader at SMK Jayawisata Jakarta, namely:

For the organizational culture variable, where the dimension that has the greatest influence on employee performance is "Self-development to get optimal results by completing work" so that based on the above, the researcher gave advice, namely school leaders at Jayawisata Jakarta Vocational High School need to make a self-development program in this conducting training in accordance with the

competencies of each teacher by better applying according to the needs of teachers of minelial and gen z. Training for Millennial and Gen Z Teachers must be tailored to the needs and characteristics of the two that are different. Here are some trainings that can be provided for Millennial and Gen Z Teachers:

- **Digital Literacy:** Generation Z workers grow up with digital technology and technology, while Millennial employees experience digital transformation as adults. That's why digital literacy training and the use of technology can help millennials and Gen Z employees use technology more effectively in the workplace.
- **Leadership:** Millennial and Generation Z workers value leadership differently than previous generations. Leadership training that teaches collaborative skills, openness, and trust can help young workers lead effectively.
- **Communication Skills :** Millennial and Generation Z workers have different communication preferences, such as using text messages or social media. Communication training can help employees improve their interactions with colleagues, clients, or customers.
- **Creativity :** Millennial and Generation Z workers tend to be very creative and value a work environment where they can innovate and collaborate. Training that teaches creative skills such as design thinking and brainstorming can help young workers innovate in the workplace.
- **Time Management :** Millennial and Generation Z workers often have many responsibilities outside of work, such as busy social activities and hobbies. Time management training can help young workers manage their time effectively and increase their productivity.
- **Specific Skills Training:** Each company has specific needs for a specific industry. Specific skills training can help millennial and Gen Z workers gain the skills they need for their jobs and improve their performance at work.

With these trainings, it can improve optimal performance in completing each work target and if this is done well it will become an organizational culture at Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta which is routinely applied. For the variable work motivation, where the dimension that has the greatest influence on employee performance is "The organization holds a Gathering for employees so that a sense of family, friendship and affection arisesso as to increase work motivation at Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta based on the above, the researcher provides the following

advice: Millennial and Gen Z teachers have a work style that is very dependent on digitalization and this is very helpful in learning and developing more updated education due to the use of digitalization. School leaders at SMK Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta need to carry out several activities related to work motivation such as:

- **The Annual Togetherness program**, namely, Gathering / Outbond to teachers regularly so that there is a sense of family and strong involvement between individuals.
- **Giving Annual Rewards**, namely The Best Teacher Performance (The Best Teacher Performance), Best Digital Teacher (Best Digital Teacher), Best Outstanding Teacher (The Best Teacher of The Year), Education Scholarship (Teacher Scholarship) and others in accordance with the criteria in the work to be motivated in improving teacher performance.

For the employee performance variable, where the dimension that has the greatest influence is "Having a good understanding and skills in carrying out work" so based on the above, the researcher gave advice, namely school leaders at Jayawisata Vocational High School Jakarta need to involve millennial and gen Z teachers to have a good understanding and skills for work. Here are some of them:

- **Technology** : Millennials are familiar with technology and understand how to use it effectively and efficiently. They can use a variety of applications and software to improve productivity and collaboration.
- **Creativity** : Millennials and Gen Z tend to have creative and innovative thinking. He knows how to think outside the box to find the best solution to complete the work task.
- **Collaboration**: Millennials and Gen Z tend to collaborate and be open to new ideas from colleagues or colleagues. They understand that cooperation skills are necessary to achieve common goals.
- **Flexibility** : Millennials and Gen Z can quickly and flexibly adapt to changing work environments. They are usually open to technological changes or new work methods and can adapt quickly.
- **Multitasking** : Millennials and Gen Z are often used for multitasking. They can perform multiple tasks effectively and efficiently.
- **English Skills** : Millennials and Gen Z tend to have good English skills. This is an advantage in the era of globalization and digitalization, where English is an international language in the work environment.

With this understanding and skills, millennials and generation z can become a productive and skilled future workforce to jointly improve various skills by using digital technology platforms to understand work procedures and work regulations by looking at the interests of each individual teacher in order to carry out work with good skills.

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